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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The CESSDA SaW (Strengthening and Widening) project task 4.5 - Development support - How to achieve CESSDA membership once established and resolving issues for former members, including addressing new national consortium structures, and taking a regional approach to building CESSDA to non-CESSDA cooperation partnerships - should report on the state and the needs of the data archive currently not being a member of the CESSDA research infrastructure.

This is the second report of the task (D4.7 being the first one) and it captures the formal mechanism of collaboration and development towards structuring a widened CESSDA network described the task 4.5. The main aim of this task was to create a collaborative structure between the CESSDA partners in a widened CESSDA network. The activities were supposed to result in a widened collaboration, promotion and implementation of CESSDA objectives at the European level. Even though the original goal was taking a regional approach for building CESSDA to non-CESSDA cooperation partnership, this aim was changed during the project. The reason for the change was the fact that many countries and their data services, have started the process of achieving CESSDA membership during the SaW project, and some acquired it, so a collaborative network parallel with CESSDA community would not be relevant. On the other hand, Saw project was supposed to produce suggestions of the ways of developing collaborations with the new data services.

The D4.8 deliverable concentrates on the expectations and possibilities of the future collaboration with the new data services in the European research area.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

ADP	Arhiv Družboslovnih Podatkov
ADS	Polish social data archive
AuSSDA	The Austrian Social Science Data Archive
CNRS	Centre Nationale de la Recherche Scientifique (Progedo)
ČSDA	Czech Social Science Data Archive
DANS	Data Archiving and Networked Services
DAS	Data Archive Service
DDA	Danish National Archive - Danish Data Archive
EKKE	Ethniko Kentro Koinonikon Erevnon
ESSDA	Estonian Social Science Data Archive
FFZG	Filozofski fakultet Sveučilišta u Zagrebu
FORS	Swiss Foundation for Research in Social Sciences
FSD	Finnish Social Science Data Archive
GERD	Gross Domestic Expenditure on Research and Development
GESIS	Leibniz Institute for the Social Sciences
ICS-ULisboa	Instituto de Ciencias Sociais da Universidade de Lisboa
IDM	Institute for democracy and mediation
IEN	Institut Ekonomskih Nauka
ISDC	Israel Social Sciences Data Centre
JESDA	Joint Economic and Social Data Archive
KIIS	Kiev International Institute of Sociology
LiDA	Lithuanian Data Archive for Humanities and Social Sciences
LISER	Luxembourg Institute of Socio-Economic Research
LSZDA	Latvian Databank of Social Sciences
NSD	Norwegian Centre for Research Data
RODA	Asociatia Arhiva Romana de Date Sociale
So.Da.Net	Greek research infrastructure for the social sciences
SOHDA	Social Sciences and Humanities Data Archive
SU-SAV	Sociologicky Ustav Slovenskej Akademie Vied
TÁRKI	TÁRKI Alapitvány (TARKI Foundation)
UCD ISSDA	University College Dublin - Irish Social Science Data Archive
UGOT-SND	University of Gothenburg - Swedish National Data Service
UKDA	UK Data Archive
UniData	Universita degli studi di Milano - Bicocca Data Archive

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report attempts to draw the current state of collaboration between the CESSDA ERIC and the non-member countries' data services in the European area. At the beginning of the CESSDA SaW project (in the August 2015) one of the biggest disadvantages CESSDA ERIC was confronted with was the low number of the future or prospective CESSDA ERIC members. Some of the previous, informal, CESSDA network members did not find a way to reach the formal CESSDA membership, and lot of new and potential service providers emerged from the previously non-CESSDA member's countries. This is why one of the main aims of the CESSDA SaW project are the widening efforts; therefore, project included a number of beneficiaries aside from the CESSDA members.

The first aim of the task 4.5 is to depict and investigate the current state and needs of the new archives of candidate countries to meet general CESSDA requirements (D4.7). Furthermore, it aims to investigate on how CESSDA ERIC and its current members could be mobilized to support strengthening and widening activities of CESSDA ERIC. The CESSDA SaW project created an opportunity to for CESSDA ERIC to look for new possible ways to establish collaboration with non-CESSDA data services. To be able to establish such connections, first it was necessary to acquire more relevant information and knowledge about the capacities of European data services outside the current CESSDA ERIC membership. To reach this aim, collaborative workshops were organized to collect the necessary input from the participating non-CESSDA data archives.

The second aim of the workshops was to build connection and collaboration network with the data services as a basis for the future work together. The workshops opened up a space to learn about the expectations of the new data archives, i.e. on how to support them in their work in general and in their mission to become a national service provider.

At the first workshop of the CESSDA SaW project (on 16 and 17th of June 2016 in Den Haag, The Netherlands) task 4.5 hosted two sessions titled 'Widening CESSDA – Development of the collaboration network of Service Providers outside of the current

CESSDA'. During the sessions, the partners formally started developing a network of collaboration of Service Providers and organizations outside of the current CESSDA membership, and the task 4.5 participants collected information on the mechanisms of expected collaboration, based first on different suggestions the sessions resulted with, and second on the identification of key stakeholders and strategies for integrating new members or build a close collaboration with CESSDA ERIC.

The target of task 4.5 are the non-CESSDA ERIC member countries, in which at least some proto-activities exist have been or are being implemented with the aim to organize a data archive service. Concerning the availability/recovery of relevant data archive services in those countries, reaching these services proved to be challenging, but thanks to the close cooperation with the task 3.2 information was acquired from those countries which are currently not part included in the CESSDA SaW project and/or not able to participate in the collaborative workshops in the project.

During the past years of the CESSDA SaW project, the list of non-member countries was updated due to many countries joining the CESSDA ERIC in that period. In some respects, these countries are comparable to the current non-member countries, but in other they differ. As a result, the Task 4.5 participants decided to keep these countries as the subject of this report, and the final list of investigated countries is as follows: Albania, Austria, Belgium, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Estonia, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Luxembourg, Macedonia (FYRM), Moldova, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia

The countries which have become CESSDA ERIC members during the project were Austria, Belgium, Hungary, Portugal, and Slovakia. Lot of the other countries, like for example Romania and Poland, have had functioning data archives from many years, but many others are just beginning the process of building their data services. To conclude, there is a range of situations with data archives and various categories of data services available, but during the SaW project the partners started making a new and widened collaborative network to support each other in the future work and projects to achieve shared goals. If the CESSDA ERIC wants to support the non-member partners, it is necessary to be aware of their needs and expectations of the future cooperation. This report introduces some information to enable the

continuation of the network building activity between the CESSDA partners, currently inside or outside the ERIC formal organization.

2. BACKGROUND OF INFORMATION REGARDING POTENTIAL SERVICE PROVIDERS' EXPECTATIONS

During the third Workshop of the SaW project in Lisbon in May 2017, the task 4.5 participants from data archives in potential member countries collected additional information by conducting the self-assessment survey. The survey consisted of two parts: the first contained questions about respondent's basic information, while the second part of the survey enabled project partners to provide information about the expected scope of the future collaboration with the CESSDA ERIC. Target group of the survey were the potential service providers/data archives gathered at the workshop.

The basic information about the data services asked in the first part of the survey was:

1. Name of Data Archive
2. Date of establishment
3. Main funding source
4. Number of persons working in the data archive
5. Current main activity (archiving, collecting survey, creating metadata system, etc.):
6. Primary aim in the near future:
7. Main difficulty with the development of the Data Archive

Given that the responses revealed their main funding sources, it was possible to classify the data services into three categories: the first group was the one that receives its funding from the ministry or the university it belongs to. The next category finances its activities by international and national projects it takes part in. The third group are the archives who have indicated they do not have any funding sources. These archives are currently not participating in any projects and/or, if operating within a university, do not have a separate budget or regular staff, but staff consist of volunteers otherwise employed by the given university.

Obtained results indicate that data services do not usually have full-time employees. This means that an employee is not involved in data service activities full-time, but in most cases, he/she is a university or research institute employee, and the data service activities are only one of his/her many daily tasks as a researcher or a teacher.

Regarding their current main activity, the new data archives define their focus mainly in connection to configuring the separate services, metadata system, or data catalogue. Those activities have been going on for longer amount of time, with the archiving and the maintaining of the existing infrastructure.

In the part where the question about the primary aim of the data archive was asked, the answers varied. The most frequent answers imply that to most common aim is to achieve stable funding or find satisfying support for operating sustainably. The second most common aim pointed out was the expansion of the data collection. Expectedly, the primary aim of the new founded data services is to establish the data archive and become a nationally relevant institution, or to create a national development plan.

As their main difficulty is slowing down the archive's functioning, the potential data services identify the financial and funding problems as the most pressing. Almost all the respondents mentioned this disadvantage. Along with this difficulty, some archives are running a battle against the bureaucratic or administrative problems in communication with the ministry or other official representative organization.

In the second part of the survey, information about the current and further collaborative network was asked. Participants were asked to describe how could CESSDA support their Data Archive activity. That question referred to the future cooperation and offered three categories of the answers: lobbying activity; involvement in projects; seminars or training support. Most of the respondents marked 'involvement in project', but the other two activities appear significant in the answers. There are few possibilities how CESSDA members can and are willing to indirectly support potential service providers in their efforts on the way to membership through sharing of know-how and trainings that CESSDA provides. In

order to do it, participants were asked to describe what kind of network support did they need from the CESSDA community.

They were also asked if they collaborated with CESSDA in the past at institutional, political level or scientific level, since many countries were indeed part of informal CESSDA organisation that was established in the 1970s. Some of the data archives have collaborated with CESSDA in the past at institutional or scientific level, but a lot of the new data services have never worked with CESSDA before. Some of the new partners have some experience collaborating with CESSDA, but this does not seem to be the rule: for the new data services the current participation in CESSDA SaW project is the first form of working with CESSDA community.

Another set of questions dealt with the of collaborative network that would be useful to institutions to develop the data archive and/or reach the CESSDA ERIC membership, as well as what kind of capacity dis they have that can be useful to the CESSDA community (e.g. human resources, sharing of national survey/datasets, metadata of the social science databases, involvement in the Question Bank, etc.). Participants were also asked about their position and chances to become a service provider in their country with possible answers spanning from weak to very strong. These were open questions, but the answers are characteristic and show that the most important aim of the SaW collaboration is the exchange of the standards and/or knowledge. The second favourable kind of collaboration is one which provides technical assistance to the recently established data services. The financial collaboration via projects is the next important part of the collaboration. Along with this, the lobbying activity proved to be one of the main tasks of the future network.

When it came to capacity that data service could offer to the CESSDA community, the answers varied in detail. Most of them addressed the following topics:

- information about national data sources
- metadata information of the datasets
- national surveys documentation
- survey datasets

- human resources by involvement in activities

The last question addressed the position of the data archive to become a service provider in its country. It is indicative that more than 85% of the respondents believed their position to be strong or very strong in their country (meaning their institutions are already a service providers). Only two respondents saw their positions as weak.

3. THE COLLABORATIVE NETWORK - SUMMARY

The 3rd CESSDA SaW Workshop entitled “Widening the European infrastructure of social science data archives” was held in Lisbon, on the 3rd and 4th of May 2017. During the workshop, an informal collaborative network between the current CESSDA members and potential partner countries was established.

This workshop was a great success with over 30 countries represented and actively contributed to all sessions. The financial, scientific and societal benefits of establishing national data services were presented, along with the present current initiatives and models for establishing data archives, and models of assistance to countries in developing national plans for establishing data archiving services (detailed program and all sessions presented in the Appendix 2).

As mentioned in the previous chapters, during this event, information on the needs of potential partners for future cooperation with CESSDA was collected. This information will be used as a basis for planning of the future collaboration so to continue the work the project partners are doing in order to build and widen CESSDA. As the analysis of the expectations and the current state of the new data service shows, there are various levels of capacity in CESSDA and the network around it, but the findings of this workshop can be presumed as a guarantee of a future collaboration and further development.

APPENDIX 1

Survey about needs of new data services in the view of the formal mechanism of collaboration and development towards structuring a widened CESSDA network

More person from one data archive can fill the questionnaire.

1. Name of Data Archive:

2. Your position in the Data Archive:

3. Country:

4. Short description of the Data Archive:

4/a. Date of establish:

4/b. Main funding source:

4/c. Number of persons working in the data archive:

4/d. Current main activity (archiving, collect survey, create metadata system, etc.):

4/e. Primary aim in the near future:

4/f. Main difficulty against the developing of the Data Archive:

5. How can CESSDA support your Data Archive activity? (More than one answer is possible)

- Lobbying activity
- Involvement in projects
- Seminars or training support
- Others, please describe:

6. This workshop aims to establish an informal collaborative network of current and potential CESSDA partners and will collect information regarding the needs of future cooperation. Please, describe what kind of network support do you need from the CESSDA community.

6/a. Did you collaborate with the CESSDA in the past at institutional, political level or scientific level? Please, describe this collaboration:

6/b. In the future what kind of collaborative network will useful to your institution to develop the data archive and/or reach the CESSDA ERIC membership?

7. What kind of capacity do you have what can be useful to the CESSDA community? (For example, human resources, share national survey/datasets, metadata of the social science databases, involvement in the Question Bank, etc.)

8. How can you describe your position to become the service provider in your country?

- Rather weak
- Weak
- Strong
- Very strong

8/a. If you see your position rather weak or weak, what do you think, what is the main reason of this?

THANK YOU FOR HELPING OUR WORK WITH YOUR ANSWERS!

APPENDIX 2

CESSDA SaW Workshop 3 sessions, programme

“Widening the European infrastructure for Social Science data archives” 3rd SaW Collaborative Workshop Programme”

3rd and 4th May 2017, Lisbon Portugal

Day 1

09.00 – 09.20 Welcome remarks (Bjørn Henrichsen, CESSDA Board of Directors, José Luís Cardoso, Director of ICS-Lisboa)

09.20 – 09.50 Aspiring CESSDA ERIC members’ perspective (Maria Fernanda Rollo, Secretary of State of Science, Technology and Higher Education, Portugal)

09.50 – 10.10 Current membership and efforts towards ERIC status (Kari Bjørke, Ministry of Education and Research, Norway)

10.40 – 11.15 The role of European Research Infrastructures in the Cloud (Antonio di Giulio, European Commission, DG Research and Innovation)

11.15 – 12.00 Capturing and communicating the value and economic impact of social science data services (Neil Beagrie, Results from the SaW project)

13.00 – 14.00 Opportunities and challenges for research data infrastructures (national archives/data services) in current non-CESSDA member countries (Janez Stebe, Brian Kleiner, Results from the SaW project)

14.00 – 15.00 Research infrastructures and research community – researchers' perspective (Adrian Dusa and Jorge Vala)

15.30 – 16.30 Panel discussion (Chair: Bjørn Henrichsen)

Capturing and communicating the value and economic impact of social science data services

Day 2

Parallel session 1 – We have a plan for developing a national data service. What's next? (Chair: Brian Kleiner)

Parallel session 2 – Steps towards a successful integration in CESSDA ERIC (Chair: Tamas Rudas)

12.00 – 12.30 Plenary discussion of results of the workshops